

Thermoelectric behavior of ZnTe materials and its characterization

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Abstract

Zinc acetate source materials and tellurium oxide are the main sources to synthesize the ZnTe Nanoparticles. By hydrothermal synthesis, zinc telluride nanoparticles are prepared and characterized by using X-ray diffractometer, Photo Luminescence Spectroscopy and Photo acoustics Spectroscopy. XRD analysis gave the result of crystal size lies within the range of 52 nm. This synthesized nano material was annealed to two different temperatures of 200^oC and 400^oC. For the annealed samples, crystal size increases to the values of 57nm and 63nm. The Ultraviolet Spectroscopy studies inferred that its absorption and bandgap values decreased and the crystal size increases. Photoacoustics spectroscopy gave the result of thermoelectric behavior of the samples. Thermal conductivity and Thermal diffusivity of the samples were calculated by using this technique.

Keywords: Zinc acetate, tellurium oxide, XRD, bandgap

References

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